

1 **Blockchain Technology for Immunization Data Storage in India: Opportunities for**
2 **Population Health Innovation**

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27 **Summary Box**

28 What are the new findings?

- 29 ● Connecting disparate immunization data storage systems can help improve the
30 value and quality of care provided.
- 31 ● Blockchain technology can improve the security and traceability of immunization
32 data in India

33 How might it impact on healthcare in the future?

- 34 ● Reducing immunization data storage complexity by designing systems with
35 stakeholder input is key to ensuring stability in large, fragmented public health
36 systems.
- 37 ● Blockchain data storage systems can be acceptable and useful for complex
38 public healthcare systems to build trust and communication.

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47 **Background**

48 Childhood vaccination is a cost-effective public health intervention with proven positive
49 outcomes on individual, community and global scales as some of the highest return of
50 investment into healthcare.¹ India's vaccination program is one of the largest in the
51 world, covering 27 million live births per year and 100 million children under age five
52 alone, but coverage is far from universal. Recent investments and improvements in
53 India's vaccine program are working to improve the rates of immunized children,
54 including the recent Mission Indradhanush.² However, immunization data in India is
55 stored in complex fragmented data storage systems that have led to mismatch in
56 resources and system-wide shortfalls. The fragmentation has been due to various
57 innovations being developed in real time in a decentralized manner.³ With the global
58 need for tracking immunization data due to the COVID-19 pandemic, solutions for
59 improving immunization data storage are critical. There is a great deal of interest
60 surrounding use cases for blockchain technology in development and healthcare.⁴
61 Blockchain, the technology underlying cryptocurrencies such as bitcoin, can be
62 especially useful in improving decentralized and error prone information storage.⁵ There
63 has been limited use of blockchain technology in the field of healthcare data
64 management despite the enthusiasm surrounding it,⁴ specifically no prior exploration of
65 the use of blockchain technology in the national storage of healthcare data. In
66 partnership with the Biotechnology and Research Council of India (BIRAC) and Gates
67 Grand Challenges India as part of the Immunization Data: Innovating for Action (IDIA)
68 program, we explored means for improvement in digitization of data through the use of
69 blockchain technology.

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71 **Needs Assessment of Indian Immunization Data Storage**

72 Exploring the current state of immunization data storage in India was crucial to avoid
73 increasing further complexity. In-depth interviews with national and state level policy
74 makers, technological partners and front-line workers were key in elucidating the current
75 needs and opportunities. Themes of data quality, ease of use, mutability of data,
76 infrastructure fault tolerance and cost were most commonly discussed. E-vin is most
77 frequently used to store supply chain data and has had many successes in
78 standardizing and improving data collection by focusing on oversight.⁶ Data size and
79 security have been a challenge with the increasing amount of centrally stored data. On
80 the beneficiary side, the data collection and storage methods varied depending on the
81 state with increasing fragmentation of data storage and frequent difficulty with collating
82 data due to network and central server failures. After a national needs assessment, our
83 prototype work was focused on Gujarat to help connect beneficiary health data from
84 TECHO+, their health data app,⁷ to supply chain side data. Invested technological
85 partners were key to assuring that the possible solutions generated through this process
86 are able to be implemented in the future.

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88 The lack of communication between the different databases and an inability to easily
89 collate this data was one of the major issues that could be helped by a blockchain
90 based solution. Blockchain technology is particularly suited to solving problems of
91 storing asynchronous data securely that can be changed from multiple touchpoints. The
92 multiple storage options that already exist in India can thus be connected using a

93 blockchain based connector system without adding more complexity to an already
94 congested landscape because blockchain technology allows for simultaneous access to
95 data from multiple touchpoints while storing the history of any data changes, thereby
96 ensuring security.

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98 **Blockchain as a Connector Database**

99 Based on an in-depth exploration of the current immunization data storage landscape,
100 the study team worked with government officials and immunization stakeholders to
101 highlight the costs and benefits of the use cases of blockchain in immunization data in
102 India and to prototype a blockchain based immunization data connector called
103 “Anveshan”. The blockchain based solution was created to solve the four underlying key
104 problems identified: 1) need for parsimonious solution to data fragmentation, 2) fault
105 tolerance, 3) data sharing with researchers, and 4) automatic incentivization for front
106 line workers to improve data quality. Since this study was determined to be a quality
107 improvement project, no institutional review was deemed necessary.

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109 Anveshan, the blockchain based connector database that was developed, connects a
110 beneficiary side and supply side databases. (Figure 1) After a survey of the
111 technological landscape, we found success with a prototype using the open source
112 Hyperledger blockchain core and GraphQL - a technology developed by Facebook’s
113 research organization that aims to enable easier more efficient data querying and
114 interaction with complex data stores and schemas.⁸ GraphQL was able to stitch
115 together different data sets with an overlapping data field allowing Anveshan to connect

116 existing siloed immunization data stores. Data security could be improved by
117 incorporating disincentives for inappropriate data modification directly into the
118 blockchain. Results from data simulations using generated data showed that the
119 Anveshan database was able to decrease data fragmentation by querying across both
120 supply and beneficiary databases. Aggregate analysis capability was increased through
121 development of a dashboard that allowed policymakers and immunization program staff
122 to receive real-time query feedback. These analyses are especially helpful in following
123 the utilization of immunization stock at a granular level to allow prediction of
124 immunization needs by village as well as decreasing vaccine waste and fraud.
125 Anveshan allowed for certain data to be downloaded after deidentification to encourage
126 innovation and research through public private partnerships. After a thorough review of
127 costs and benefits, a private blockchain database was suggested as the optimal
128 solution to balance between benefits like fault tolerance and cost. Each state data
129 repository could be a separate node on the blockchain to ensure quality while ensuring
130 more local control of data to improve data accessibility and upload.

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132 **Blockchain in Immunization Data: Costs and Benefits**

133 The need for tracking vast amounts of immunization data is an especially important
134 imperative now with the need for ensuring efficient distribution and utilization of COVID-
135 19 vaccines in a country as vast as India. Blockchain technology can be particularly
136 helpful in an already complex and fragmented data storage system in India by allowing
137 for greater security by storing multiple copies of immutable data. However, the
138 connecting database and a blockchain solution has not been implemented in practice

139 due to real world acceptance and scalability problems. Balancing the needs and
140 motivations of a complex landscape of stakeholders remains a challenge to ensure that
141 new technologies can be implemented. Initial buy-in from the primary owners of the
142 immunization data would have made faster implementation of the technological
143 interventions described here. There are a variety of existing blockchain technologies,
144 and trade-offs are unique to each problem. Blockchains cannot inherently solve the
145 problem of faulty data but can be useful in ensuring the security/integrity of the data
146 after it is stored. Especially in settings with significant variability of reliability of internet
147 connections, distributed fault resistant data storage systems like blockchain can ensure
148 data doesn't get lost as a result of technology infrastructure issues. Blockchain
149 technology also brings strong data privacy guarantees through the strong encryption
150 schemes that are used in the private-public key based accounts that are at the core of
151 modern blockchains.

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153 For healthcare data storage, the fundamental trade-off occurs between security and
154 efficiency. Private blockchains are more efficient and cheaper while still preserving a lot
155 of fault tolerance and transparency of their public counterparts. Having multiple servers
156 across India on the national, state, and locality level participating in the blockchain will
157 enable significant fault tolerance that will be able to sustain a subset of servers failing,
158 unreliable internet connections, and other issues plaguing data storage in this vast, low
159 resource environment. We have seen so far that blockchains provide unique benefits
160 and could be powerful as a backbone for a national or state level data, but architecture
161 and configuration matters. A wholistic approach to studying the development and

162 implementation of a new technology in healthcare data storage can be emulated to
163 ensure thoughtful introduction of new technologies as a means to add value to the
164 healthcare landscape.

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166 **Contributorship:**

167 All persons who meet authorship criteria are listed as authors, and all authors certify
168 that they have participated sufficiently in the work to take public responsibility for the
169 content, including participation in the concept, design, analysis, writing, or revision of
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184 Figure 1. Schematic of data systems connecting with Anveshan.

185 Figure 2. Schematic diagram illustrating data storage structure for proposed private
186 blockchain immunization data storage for Gujarat, India. Example data IDs are utilized
187 to illustrate the nodes in the blockchain storage schematic.

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